

ORIGINAL PAPER

Effects of potentization in aqueous solutions

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Over the past two decades, research into structure formation and structure conservation in water has created a significant interest among the homeopathy research community. The formation of sustained static and dynamic structures in aqueous solutions is thought to be synonymous with the possible storage of information in associated liquids. Prominent models and experiments considering this possibility are presented in this paper, and some of their subtleties, which were not given much room in the respective original publications, will be elucidated in more detail here.

Keywords: aqueous solutions; structure; order; information; fundamental research; theoretical model; experimental evidence; commercial claims

Introduction

Clinical trials and homeopathic pathogenetic trials (HPTs, provings) of homeopathic remedies address the efficacy of homeopathic remedies and, only indirectly, the complex mechanism of information storage in the associated liquid carrier used in these trials (aqueous dilutions, alcoholic dilutions, etc.). In recent years, as research into homeopathy has gained more interest among the fundamental research academic community, some interesting studies discussing possible pathways of stable information storage in such dilutions have been presented.

Homeopathy, as a research subject, is inherently multi-disciplinary. It is thus no surprise that a range of different attempts have been made to establish some understanding of the processes that may be interpreted as information transfer or information storage. In academic research circles, most criticism of the validity of homeopathy focused on the issue of ultra high dilutions where concentrations below the Avogadro limit are applied. The criticism placed promoters of homeopathy in a very difficult situation for only arguments based on well-accepted fundamental scientific grounds are acceptable by the peer-reviewed academic community. In the early days of fundamental research into homeopathy, only those promoters who happen to have old high-school books on physics

on their shelf were able to formulate possible alternative pathways of information storage. Initially, those 'alternative pathways' were more of the 'hand-waving' nature than anything acceptable to academic science: this was quite natural considering the limited background. Nevertheless, this early work was quite stimulating and resulted in an increase in discussions about the fundamental mechanism of the reactive power of homeopathic remedies—a discussion that eventually spilled over to a well-equipped academic fundamental research community. Today a number of experimental results and theories have been published, some of which can stand up to most of the severe scrutiny of the academic science community. National and international organizations in homeopathy played a major role in the development of high standards in research and publication practice, notably the European Committee for Homeopathy (ECH).

Any fundamental research into homeopathy has to address the problem of apparent information transfer and information storage in aqueous solutions, as well as the subsequent mechanism of transfer to a physiological system. There is a general perception among the research community that information may be stored in some sort of *order* or *structure* in the fabric of the information carrier, in this case the aqueous solution. As potentization moves to higher dilution levels, interaction between solute and solution passes a level where very local atomistic interaction dominates the *order* controlling parameters until, at even higher dilutions and beyond the Avogadro limit, the solution alone takes control of conversion of

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information into *order* parameters. From the fundamental research point of view, an understanding of possible order formation at an atomistic level is essential for any further progress in homeopathy.

Possible order formation at the local atomistic, solute-solvent level is the basis for many theories which have been developed over past years. Order formation appears to be a clue to homeopathy. It should be measurable by way of standard experiments as well as predictable by atomistic calculations, independent of the nature and manifestation of the order parameters. In that sense, most experiments try to test theories which are based on one of the two main hypotheses, namely an order formation based on a static local *geometric* consideration or order formation based on stable *dynamic* properties. In the following we summarize the basic concepts of a few prominent geometric theories, followed by an analysis of recent experiments and comments on a new crop of commercial hoaxes.

The fact that local as well as some global structure can be formed has been discussed in a vast amount of literature on water and associated liquids. The following section discusses some prominent views on how a local structure as carrier of information may contribute to the formation of global structures.

Geometric models

Early theories concerning the possible formation of stable global structures in water were mostly based on somewhat physical-philosophical approaches, as can be found for instance in the earlier work by Popp.^{1,2}

One of the more prominent works focusing on local order formation in liquids was presented by Anagnostatos³ in his replicating clathrate model. In this model, the local structure is thought to have been developed through an externally-induced fluctuation or through deliberate contamination. The structure, in the form of a cluster, is thought to lead to a formation of local short range order, which in a secondary process forms so-called clathrates (expanded clusters enclosing smaller cluster clathrates inside). The clathrates are then assumed to be the mould for the reproduction of the original cluster structure, hence providing the means for the replication of a certain order. This model of structure formation allows an initial structure (information) to disintegrate after a certain (short) lifetime due to thermal fluctuations, while information is preserved by replication through subsequent clathrates formation. The local order parameters, or potential carriers of distinct information, are then the characteristic clathrate bond angles and bond lengths. From a theoretical point of view the existence of clathrates can be well justified. Such clathrates must exist in reasonable quantities in the homeopathic dilution in order to be of any subsequent physiological consequence. This implies that clathrates in homeopathic dilutions ought to be detectable with standard

spectroscopic techniques. So far, no such experimental evidence has been reported.

Berezin⁴ proposed an even more fundamental approach to order formation in the sense that he went further down the hierarchy of the physical scale, that is, by moving from an atomistic approach to nuclear properties. In Berezin's model, the interaction of atomically identical, isotopically different, atoms forms the basis of an ordered framework. The sequence of isotopic diversity (isotopicity) becomes the core order parameter associated with information storage. It is worthwhile to note that it is not possible to directly influence the 'isotopic coding' by simple, electromagnetic means for the simple reason that at the nuclear level, nuclear forces are required to manipulate nuclear properties such as isotopicity. However, an indirect influence is thought to be possible by electromagnetic coupling to the hydrogen bonds and hydrogen nuclear magnetic moment.

Unfortunately, Berezin's model starts at a point where a distinct order has already been established, that is, information being stored. It does not indicate a pathway of how a certain order has been achieved in the first place, or how isotopicity is propagated starting with an initial contaminant. In Berezin's model, any 'energetic' information that a contaminant carries in the form of its characteristic atomic and isotopic features relative to the 'blank' liquid would have to propagate throughout the liquid to cause the required cascade of spatial rearrangement of relative isotope locations within the liquid. This would cause a global phase transition, an effect which ought to be observable in the change of the specific heat of the liquid and maybe even in some temperature shift as energy is required for the spatial rearrangement process. Though very small changes in specific heat and temperature can be measured with high accuracy, so far such an effect has not been reported in literature.

Dynamic Models

In more recent years, static geometric models have evolved into so-called dynamic models. One of the more prominent models has been presented by Del Giudice and Preparata.⁵⁻⁷ Del Giudice and Preparata showed that in condensed matter electromagnetic fields may be 'trapped' in coherent regions and that the state of matter containing coherent regions is more stable than that of matter without coherent regions. Coherent regions, which can occupy a volume of some $10^6 \text{ \AA}^3$, can give rise to condensation by way of the coordinated oscillation of molecules accompanied by emission of respective characteristic electromagnetic fields. Through the formation of regions with electromagnetic *coherence* (electromagnetic waves with well-defined relative phase), condensed matter can, for a long time, remain in a state which is more stable than the non-coherent region. In their calculations, Del Giudice and Preparata showed that

an external electric field can create metastable extended polarization fields in a coherently moving system of water molecules. In principle, it should therefore be possible to create low frequency long-lived polarization fields in water, and even to modulate already existing coherent fields, by way of an external field (for example, the field of a contaminant). An interesting feature of this model is that it does not necessarily rely on a particular underlying 'seed' geometry, or local architecture, where information may find its vehicle for propagation. The mere existence of a specific coherence phase within domains can serve as information carrier, opening up the possibility for an electromagnetic field to create coherent regions without mediation of a contaminant. In other words, there is no need for an original mother tincture here. Though this model appears to be well founded, one has to keep in mind that a theoretical, very ideal liquid under ideal conditions is the basis for the existence of such coherence, a fact which also explains why this model has not yet been taken up for experimental verification.

Kratky⁸ moved even further away from a geometric hypothesis. He showed that the dynamic of aqueous solutions and the stability of organic systems can be described as dynamic *complex systems* with all the features inherent to complex system theory and chaos theory. According to Kratky a dynamic system can be perturbed or stabilized by a feedback mechanism, forcing an instability to stay on a dynamic attractor trajectory. The dynamic attractor will then maintain a certain converging path toward the system's point of stability, all in a well-defined way.

Though from the dynamic system point of view the attractor parameters are well-defined to the extent that the dynamics becomes even deterministic, it is very difficult to link this mathematical construct to thermodynamics or energetics of an associated liquid and its subsequent exposure to a physiological system. The parameters of an attractor in dynamic systems theory are extremely sensitive, to the extent that even the smallest change will move it away from a stable orbit. Thinking about the traditional succussion process in remedy preparation, it can hardly be imagined that an attractor can be kept on stable orbit for even a short time. Only at a point where, in a non-trivial physical system, an attractor can be successfully controlled by experimental means will it be possible to assess the relevance of dynamic systems theory to the field of homeopathy.

At a more abstract level, Xu and Bishop⁹ tried to address the problem of the missing link between dynamic systems theory and a thermodynamic system. They looked at the possibility of reconstructing information from the dynamics of a thermal system to eventually determine parameters useful for the controlled manipulation of the system. According to Xu and Bishop, all that is needed for extracting information from a dynamic system are several series of

pieces of phase space data from which the dynamics of the total system can be reconstructed, and with which it can be stabilized in a certain state by way of a suitable feedback mechanism. This ingenious procedure can be employed without any explicit knowledge of the dynamics of a particular system, or its physical boundary condition. Xu and Bishop found that only very small feedback amplitudes are necessary in order to stabilize a chaotic system by way of using the dynamic feedback mechanism, thus supporting Kratky's conclusion regarding the constructive, external stabilization or manipulation of biological systems. At present, the principal feedback mechanism is still a mathematical construct. The experimental realization of this model is very challenging and yet to be carried out. In the end, with respect to the dilution and succussion process in homeopathy, it is difficult to see where such a feedback mechanism would occur or be kept stable and undisturbed by the inherent thermodynamics and mechanical disturbances that homeopathic medicines experience during the preparation process as well as during their shelf life.

A mesoscopic model of intra-molecular interaction leading to distinct order parameters was reported by the author in Schulte and Endler¹⁰ referring to an earlier work by Käiväräinen.¹¹ The main thrust of this work is the formation of coherent stable excitations of groups of atoms, which have already formed stable aggregations of rigid or even loosely bound molecules. In this sense, the model falls into the category of dynamic models. From the theoretical point of view these excitations can then be treated as quasi-particles similar to the phonons well-known in solid state physics or the quasi-particles known in nuclear physics (a quasi-particle is a real, well-measurable physical entity). As with those quasi-particles, the proposed mechanism of quasi-particle formation can be predicted and measured as 'fingerprints' in their respective energy spectrum, in this case the infrared region. Initially, the mesoscopic resonances (quasi-particles) were aimed at explaining biological cell behaviour as well as macromolecular docking guidance, however, it was also found useful when applied to other phenomena at the mesoscopic physical scale, such as semiconductors or, in this case, homeopathy. So far, the mesoscopic model has been a mere challenge to the theorist, however, it gives clear directions for the experimentalist as to how and what needs to be measured.

Fundamental experimental work

On the experimental front, geometric models seems always to have been the underlying hypothesis of research. Accordingly, static order parameters are the subject of most investigations. In a recent publication Lu *et al*^{12,13} reported measurements of dipole-based water structures with some resemblance to those theoretically predicted by Del Giudice and

Preparata. However, existence of coherence was not a prerequisite of their reported findings. Lu's findings are based on the presence of ions (impurities) or dielectric contamination, thus their proposed model is applicable only in the range of homeopathic high (non-ultra molecular) dilutions whereas the Del Giudice and Preparata model is valid for ultra-high dilutions. Lu *et al* measured the ultra-violet (UV) absorbance of NaCl, HNO₃ and NaOH in liquid water at concentrations between 10⁻³ M and 10⁻¹³ M (concentrations as low as 10⁻¹⁵ M can be measured with high accuracy). A characteristic decrease in UV absorbance was found with similar behaviour for all three solutes at concentrations below 10⁻⁶ M. The magnitude of absorbance was differentiated from the control water sample by less than one order of magnitude and results were presented on a double logarithmic scale. Unfortunately, in the publication, error bars were not presented or discussed in the graphs, which makes an assessment of the relevance of the findings difficult.

Nevertheless, the original interpretation of data is interesting. The interpretation of the experiments is as follows: When an ionic substance is dissolved in water, the free ions present strong electrostatic fields. Because of the extremely high dielectric constant of water ($\epsilon_r \approx 80$), the electrostatic field of ions has a strong impact on the energy density of surrounding water molecules. The first layer of water molecules around an ion will experience electrostatic polarization by the ion. The molecules' total polarization will cancel, however, if the molecules are arranged symmetrically in a spherical manner about the ion. Thus, because of the Gauss' law of electrostatics, the immediate next layer of water molecules will experience an energy density boosted by a factor of 80. The energy density (energy per volume), is nothing other than the pressure experienced by the water molecules—in other words, the water molecules very close to the ion experience extremely high pressure, causing them to freeze like an ice crystal, only with a very distinct and different crystal structure from ordinary ice crystals. Due to the polarization of the 'frozen' water molecules in the immediate vicinity of the ions, the so formed local rigid structure in water can present thermally very stable dipoles. The pressure around the ion region decreases rapidly (r^{-2}) with increasing distance r from the ion. Note that this is an electrostatic effect and no electromagnetic radiation is involved. When two similarly charged ions come close together, the pressure on water molecules between them decreases and the spherical 'ice' structure will melt. As the ions move away, pressure builds up again. Thus there will be a continuous process of destruction and growth of highly ordered water structures (crystals). When considering the growth rate of 'ice' crystals and mean collision rate of ions in water (destruction), an ion concentration can be calculated at which the growth rate of crystal structures is higher

than the destruction rate. This, of course, can be expected at very low ion concentrations. Assuming a fairly fast growth rate (of the order of cm/s), Lu estimated that the polarized crystals are stable if the ion concentration is lower than 10⁻⁵ M. Lu *et al* also showed that a non-ionic dielectric medium dissolved in water produced similar 'spherical' local 'ice'-structures emphasizing the structure-stabilizing effect of polarized regions in potentized water.

Unfortunately, the dielectric medium in Lu's experiment was not specified and respective UV absorbance versus molar concentrations were not shown. Also, UV absorbance measurement of potentized unsuccussed water was not shown—this could have elucidated the influence of the succussion process. Error bars in the experimental data were also omitted, which is unfortunate because an apparent effect that manifests itself in a discrimination of data within one order of magnitude (and less) is especially important when data is presented using a double logarithmic graph.

In Lu's model a dielectric seed medium is essential for the growth of well-defined highly stable local structures. The model is based on pure electrostatics with the dynamics coming in through ion-ion collisions, which destroy previously stable structures. This, of course, implies that at ultra-high dilutions, where we expect the complete absence of ionic contaminants, the ionic seed mechanism of distinct structure formation ceases to exist. Thus, at higher dilutions, a different mechanism of order formation is called for. Since the mechanism of information preservation changes at the transition between high dilutions (< 10⁻²⁴ M) and ultra-high dilutions (> 10⁻²⁴ M), it is quite likely that the original information content also experiences a corresponding transition or change. The experiments by Bastide¹⁴ show some indications of a transition of this kind. An essential element in Bastide's interpretation is, however, the assumption that a 'non-local sense' is present in a physiological system while Lu's model relies on strong, short-range interaction. A long-range non-local interaction in a physiological system, on other hand, raises the possibility of frequent physiological breakdown, an effect which in this context has not been observed experimentally in a reproducible way.

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) seems to be an experimental technique that has been tried on homeopathic dilutions more frequently than any other measurement technique. Nevertheless, research reporting NMR measurements in homeopathy is still at a level of only a handful of publications per year. One of the pioneering works in this area was by Smith and Boericke.¹⁵ The main observables in NMR experiments are the nuclear relaxation times T_1 and T_2 of magnetically stimulated protons in hydrogen atoms. The relaxation time describes the return to the equilibrium of the nuclear magnetism following a perturbation, ie. the NMR stimulating pulse. The

spin-lattice relaxation time (T_1) characterizes the return of the M_z component of the nuclear magnetization to its equilibrium value. This indicates the leakage of the excitation energy absorbed by the spin system back into the surroundings (the underlying local lattice structure). The deuterium nucleus has a spin of $>1/2$ (e.g. spin = 1) and hence has an electric quadrupole moment in addition to its magnetic dipole moment. The interaction of the nuclear quadrupole moment with an electric field gradient provides a very efficient process for nuclear relaxation via molecular rotation. Therefore, the deuterium T_1 measurement gives a straightforward estimate of the corresponding re-orientation correlation time. Hence, in many experiments deuterium relaxation is measured instead of hydrogen.

One has to be very meticulous in these experiments, because T_1 values are very prone to systematic errors such as the presence of traces of paramagnetic impurities (e.g. transition metal ions) and dissolved gases. Therefore, care must be taken to remove these impurities by precipitation or degassing procedures prior to the actual experiment. Not many publications on NMR experiments in homeopathy report the measures that have been taken to avoid these problems which, of course, makes it difficult to interpret results. In a carefully prepared experiment the relaxation time can be considered the fingerprint of a substance and, to some extent, its embedding lattice or solution. A change in relaxation time implies that the original pure substance is either contaminated with a different substance and/or the relative structural order or orientation within the liquid has changed. In homeopathic terms the latter would be the indicator for order formation due to a dilution-succussion process. It is, however, very difficult in NMR experiments to discriminate between effects originated in small shifts in concentration (dilution) and effects due to mechanical alterations such as succussion. Apart from the difficulty in designing a NMR experiment involving homeopathic dilutions, almost all reported experiments fail to report important parameters usually mentioned in NMR measurements, which makes it even more difficult to assess the significance of the reported results.

Weingartner¹⁶ conducted NMR experiments on a range of dilutions of potentized sulphur in an ethanol solution. Relaxation times showed a trend within the large range of error margins. However, results did not permit a conclusive interpretation. Interesting NMR measurements have been reported by Demangeat *et al.*¹⁷ In this study, NMR relaxation times of silica potentizations were measured. The results are similarly difficult to interpret as those by Weingartner. Unfortunately, to the knowledge of the author, no comparable independent repeat measurements were reported in either cases. More recent NMR measurements involving potentizations of *Nux vomica* in ethanol were reported by Sukul *et al.*¹⁸ Mice treated with *Nux vomica* dilutions appeared to show a sig-

nificant reaction compared to a control group. A correlation with the T_1 relaxation of deuterium in the dilutions was reported. While this experiment is one of the more carefully conducted, the interpretation of the reported relaxation times needs further thought. An independent verification of the NMR measurements would certainly be very helpful, even without a parallel trial on mice.

Commercial claims

On the more entrepreneurial side of exploiting homeopathy for commercial purposes, some inventive researchers have produced their own framework of apparent fundamental knowledge about how information might be stored in homeopathic remedies. Within their proprietary framework the fundamental mechanism of how homeopathy works, of course, supports the respective product that goes along with their theory.

There are two chief observations to make about these attempts. The first is that one fundamental mechanism claimed to drive information storage in homeopathy is almost completely contradictory to that of a competing product, which in itself ought to appear somewhat odd even to the non-technical observer. Another observation is that none of the inventors can show a record of peer-reviewed publications in scientific journals about their findings. The hand waving argument that scientific journals would not publish such findings is one of the past, a fact as is shown in the reference list of this as well as many other articles and recent peer-reviewed books.

One of the more prominent of these products (and how a carefully disguised theory can collapse with the mere help of an undergraduate physics text book) is discussed in detail in Schulte,¹⁹ an article which also shows how easily even large investors can be misled by a flood of scientific terms, a very unfortunate development.

Conclusion

Over recent years, fundamental research into homeopathy has become more sophisticated and systematic in its approach. The coordination of research under the guidance of global research communities such as the European Committee for Homeopathy (ECH) has helped greatly. Every improvement of the fundamental understanding of how homeopathy works at the atomistic level will be invaluable to homeopathy as a whole, from the manufacturer to the practitioner and, ultimately, the patient.

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